

Computational Investigation of Nonlinear Optical Properties of Sulphamic Acid Using DFT and Multi-Model Polarizability Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Pure sulphamic acid (SA) crystals were analyzed through a comprehensive computational approach to explore their structural and nonlinear optical (NLO) characteristics. Geometry optimization and thermal stability assessments were performed using Density Functional Theory (DFT), confirming the stability of the SA molecule. Dipole moment, quadrupole moment, and isotropic polarizability (α_s) were calculated to evaluate molecular polarization relevant to optical response. Electronic polarizability was estimated using multiple theoretical models, Penn model, Clausius–Mossotti relation, optical band gap analysis, and the Coupled Dipole Method, providing deeper insights into SA's dielectric and optical behavior. The findings reinforce the suitability of sulphamic acid as a stable and cost-effective candidate for photonic and optoelectronic device applications.

Keywords: - Density Functional Theory, Molecular polarization, Electronic polarizability, Nonlinear optics, Optoelectronics.

1. Introduction

Sulphamic acid (H_3NSO_3) is a structurally simple yet functionally significant inorganic compound with a wide range of industrial, nonlinear optical device fabrications, and analytical applications[1], [2]. It is known for its zwitterionic character in aqueous solutions, along with strong hydrogen bonding and thermal stability[3], [4], [5]. These properties, combined with its non-hygroscopic and mildly acidic nature, make sulphamic acid a valuable material in nonlinear optics and photonics applications [6], [7], [8]. Despite its broad practical usage, its molecular and electronic behavior at the quantum level remains underexplored, especially in the context of optical materials research.

In recent years, nonlinear optics (NLO) has become a rapidly advancing field due to its crucial role in developing ultrafast optical devices and next-generation photonic technologies. Materials exhibiting significant nonlinear optical properties are indispensable for a variety of advanced applications such as optical switching, frequency conversion, electro-optic modulation, laser safety devices, and high-density optical data storage [9], [10], [11]. A key requirement for such materials is their ability to respond nonlinearly to intense electromagnetic fields. Sulphamic acid, with its inherent zwitterionic structure and robust molecular framework, has shown potential as a nonlinear optical material[12], [13]. Its compatibility with crystal growth techniques and ability to incorporate dopants further enhance its relevance in NLO material development [3], [4].

Traditionally, the assessment of NLO properties has relied heavily on experimental synthesis and characterization. However, the emergence of computational chemistry, especially density functional theory (DFT), has revolutionized this approach. DFT offers a cost-effective and accurate method for probing the electronic structure, molecular geometry, frontier molecular orbitals (HOMO–LUMO), vibrational frequencies, and other key parameters such as dipole moment, polarizability, and first hyperpolarizability[14], [15], [16], [17]. These theoretical descriptors are directly linked to the NLO activity of a molecule and provide valuable insights into its

α	90°	90°	90°
β	90°	90°	90°
γ	90°	90°	90°
Volume (\AA^3)	603	604.6926	605.79
System	Orthorhombic	Orthorhombic	Orthorhombic
Space group	Pbca	Pbca	Pbca

2.2 Molecular Geometry Optimisation

The ground-state molecular geometry of sulphamic acid (SA) was optimized using density functional theory (DFT) with the B3LYP hybrid functional and the 6-11G(d,p) basis set, as implemented in ORCA 5.0. This level of theory provides an accurate balance between computational efficiency and electronic structure prediction, particularly for hydrogen bonding and zwitterionic systems. The optimization process converged to a stable minimum-energy configuration, confirmed by the absence of imaginary frequencies in vibrational analysis. The Optimised Geometry and packing fraction of Sulphamic acid is shown in Figure 2.

Fig -2: a) Optimized molecular geometry of SA b) Packing of SA

2.3 Computational Thermal Analysis

The thermal analysis of Sulphamic acid (H_3NSO_3) was conducted using Density Functional Theory (DFT) with the B3LYP functional, offering valuable insights into its thermodynamic stability and energetic variations under different temperature and pressure conditions. The computed thermochemical parameters internal energy (U), enthalpy (H), entropy (S), and Gibbs free energy (G) provide a comprehensive description of the material's thermal behavior[18]. These parameters are critical for understanding the thermodynamic stability and reactivity of Sulphamic acid under varying environmental conditions. The internal energy remains relatively constant across different pressures at a given temperature, indicating the robustness of the electronic structure under external perturbations. This suggests that the molecular framework of Sulphamic acid is resilient to changes in pressure, which is a desirable property for materials used in high-pressure applications. Enthalpy, calculated as $H = U + k_B T$, exhibits minimal variations with pressure, further reinforcing the system's thermodynamic stability. Entropy, which accounts for vibrational, rotational, and translational contributions, increases with temperature, reflecting the expected rise in molecular motion and disorder[19], [20]. The variation of entropy with temperature at different pressures is illustrated in Figure 3.

Further, a slight decrease in entropy with increasing pressure suggests a reduction in molecular freedom, which could influence the material's optical and structural properties. This behavior aligns with the principles of statistical thermodynamics, where increased pressure typically restricts molecular motion, leading to lower entropy. The Gibbs free energy, derived from $G = H - T \cdot S$, decreases with increasing temperature, indicating enhanced thermodynamic feasibility at rising temperatures.

Fig -3: Computational Thermal Analysis of SA by using B3LYP Functionals.

The decrease in Gibbs free energy with temperature also implies that the compound becomes more thermodynamically favorable for reactions or phase transitions as temperature rises[20], [21]. The thermal stability and consistent thermodynamic parameters of Sulphamic acid highlight its potential for nonlinear optical applications and photonic device fabrication.

2.4 Electronic polarizability (α^*) for Pure SA.

The electronic polarizability (α^*) is a fundamental parameter that describes the response of a material's electron cloud to an external electric field. It plays a crucial role in determining the nonlinear optical properties of the material[22], [23]. A material's electronic polarizability (α^*) is directly influenced by its dielectric constant. The valence electron plasma energy ($\hbar\omega_p$), Penn gap (E_p), and Fermi energy (E_f) also depend on the material's dielectric constant. The density of SA is calculated using the formula:

$$\rho = \frac{M \cdot Z}{N_A \cdot V} \quad \dots(1)$$

where: $M=97.10$ g/mol (molecular weight of SA(H_3NSO_3)), $Z=4$ (number of molecules per unit cell for SA), $N_A=6.022 \times 10^{23}$ mol⁻¹ (Avogadro's number), $V = 603 \times 10^{-24}$ cm³ (volume of the unit cell). Crystal density is found to be 2.14 g/cm³. The valence electron plasma energy is calculated as:

$$\hbar\omega_p = 28.8 \left(\frac{Z' \cdot \rho}{M} \right)^{1/2} \quad \dots(2)$$

where $Z'=32$ (total number of valence electrons in SA: H=3, N=5, S=6, O=18). The Penn gap and Fermi energy are calculated using:

$$E_p = \frac{\hbar\omega_p}{\sqrt{\epsilon' - 1}} \quad \dots(3)$$

$$E_f = 0.2948(\hbar\omega_p)^{4/3} \quad \dots(4)$$

where $\epsilon'=18.23$ (dielectric constant of SA).

The electronic polarizability is calculated using the Penn model [22], [23] as,

$$\alpha_1 = \left[\frac{\hbar\omega_p^2 \cdot S_0}{(\hbar\omega_p^2 \cdot S_0) + 3 E_p^2} \right] \cdot \frac{M}{\rho} \cdot 0.396 \cdot 10^{-24} \text{ cm}^3 \quad \dots(5)$$

where S_0 is a constant calculated as:

$$S_0 = 1 - \frac{E_p}{4E_f} + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{E_p}{4E_f} \right) \quad \dots(6)$$

Similarly, we can calculate the electronic polarizability (α_2) using the Clausius-Mossotti relation as

$$\alpha_2 = \frac{3M}{4\pi N_A} \left[\frac{\epsilon_0 - 1}{\epsilon_0 + 2} \right] \quad \dots(7)$$

The electronic polarizability is also calculated using the optical band gap energy ($E_g=5.19$ eV for SA):

$$\alpha_3 = \left[1 - \frac{\sqrt{E_g}}{4.06} \right] \cdot \frac{M}{P} \cdot 0.396 \cdot 10^{-24} \text{ cm}^3 \quad (8)$$

Renne and Nijboer introduced the coupled dipole method (CDM) to analyze the electronic polarizability of materials, as

$$\alpha_4 = \frac{Z' * e}{m_e * \omega_0^2} \left[\frac{\epsilon_0 - 1}{\epsilon_0 + 2} \right] \quad \dots(9)$$

Where $Z'=32$ (total valence electrons), $e=1.602 \times 10^{-19}$ C (electron charge), $m_e = 9.1 \times 10^{-28}$ g (electron mass), $\omega_0=2\pi f$ rad/s (frequency at 100 KHz). The electronic polarizability values at different temperatures are given in Table 2.

Table No.2 Comparison of Electronic Polarizability and Related Parameters

Parameters	Values for SA	Values of KDP Crystal [22]
Plasma energy ($\hbar\omega_p$)	24.14 eV	17.33 eV
Penn gap energy (E_p)	5.82 eV	2.39 eV
Fermi energy (E_F)	31.68 eV	12.02 eV
Electronic polarizability (α_1) (Penn analysis)	1.525×10^{-23} cm ³	2.14×10^{-23} cm ³
Electronic polarizability (α_2) (Clausius-Mossotti)	1.533×10^{-23} cm ³	2.18×10^{-23} cm ³
Electronic polarizability (α_3) (Optical band gap)	7.89×10^{-24} cm ³	–
Electronic polarizability (α_4) (CDM)	2.285×10^{-23} cm ³	–

To understand the electronic properties computationally, a DFT approach has been taken, and electronic properties like dipole moment (μ_{tot}), quadrupole moment, and isotropic polarizability were calculated using TD-DFT functionals. Calculated values of all components and their resultants of dipole moment and polarizability are given in Table 3 [where 1 a.u. = 1.4818×10^{-25} cm³]. The respective value of μ_{tot} is found to be **2.3 times higher** than urea [$\mu_{Urea}=0.5402$ a.u.][24]. Hence, the computational analysis suggests that the studied molecule (SA) exhibits significant dipole moment and polarizability, making it a potential candidate for nonlinear optical (NLO) applications.

Table No.3 Electronic property calculation by using DFT

Property	Magnitude (a.u.)	Isotropic Value (cm ³)
Dipole Moment	1.55258	-
Quadrupole Moment	-26.70480	-
Isotropic Polarizability α_5	39.04749	5.786×10^{-24} cm ³

The electronic polarizability of the SA molecule, calculated using different theoretical approaches, shows remarkable consistency and highly promising values. Excellent agreement between analytical equations and DFT-based calculations underscores the robustness of the computational models and the molecule's well-defined electronic structure. The high polarizability values highlight the SA molecule's exceptional ability to undergo electronic distortion under an applied electric field, a critical property for nonlinear optical (NLO) materials.

This strong electronic response positions the SA molecule as a highly promising candidate for advanced NLO applications, such as optical switching and frequency doubling. The consistency across methods reinforces confidence in these predictions, showcasing their potential for real-world optoelectronic devices. The balanced and robust electronic distribution further suggests efficient interaction with light and external fields, making it ideal for next-generation NLO technologies.

3. Conclusion

A comprehensive computational investigation of pure sulphamic acid (SA) was performed using Density Functional Theory (DFT) to explore its structural, electronic, and optical characteristics pertinent to nonlinear optical (NLO) applications. The optimized molecular geometry and thermodynamic parameters confirm the intrinsic stability of the molecule. The calculated dipole moment, quadrupole moment, and isotropic polarizability (α_5) indicate strong intermolecular interactions and notable polarization, which are favorable traits for optical switching and modulation. Also, electronic polarizability was evaluated through multiple theoretical frameworks, including the Penn model, Clausius–Mossotti relation, optical band gap method, and coupled dipole method, providing a multidimensional perspective on SA's dielectric and optical response. These results collectively establish sulphamic acid as a structurally stable, electronically active, and computationally validated candidate for future use in photonic and optoelectronic device applications.

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